

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B092
 Date: 09 May 2005
 Take Off 11:04:48 17:05:53
 Landing: 16:08:56 17:39:00
 Flight Time 5h04m08 0h33m07

Campaign: AMPEP
Trials Instructions: UK Clockwise Circumnavigation
Operating Area: Round east and southern England (refuel at Cardiff)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Aircraft Scientist	Eiko Nemitz	CEH Edinburgh
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Mission Scientist Training	Jonathan Smith	Leeds University
6	Mission Scientist Training	Ute Skiba	CEH Edinburgh
7	PTRMS	Anne Hulse	UEA
8	Filters	Paul James	FAAM
9	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
10	WAS	Maria Nielsdottir	UEA
11	WAS	James Hopkins	University of York
12	AMS	James Allan	University of Manchester
13	Air Sample Bags	Ivan Simmons	CEH Edinburgh
14	Air Sample Bags	Alan McDonald	CEH Edinburgh
15	NOxy	David Stewart	UEA
16	CCM2 Training	Jim Crawford	FAAM
17	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B092 Track 09-MAY-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b092
 Date: 09/05/05
 Project: AMPEP
 Location: Round E & S England, refuel @ Cardiff

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
094648		Start posn	0.00 kft	125	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
104426		INU to NAV	0.26 kft	125	
110448		T/O	1.8 kft	194	From Cranfield
110622		ASPs	2.5 kft	221	OPEN
111842		Videos	10.0 kft	012	Start FFC & DFC
112107	115151	Run 1	10.0 kft	015	NOXY & Filter cals
115934	120943	Profile 1	10.0 - -.03 kft	334	1000fpm to 50'
121305	122257	Run 2	0.89 - 0.82 kft	039	1000ft
122326	124508	Run 3	0.76 - 0.88 kft	089	800ft
124030		In Run 3	0.85 kft	356	Slow turn reciprocal
124656	124709	Profile 2	0.05 - 0.10 kft	273	50' to 100'
124710	124810	Run 4	0.10 kft	272	100'
124817	124858	Profile 2	0.13 - 0.46 kft	272	100' - 500'
124859	125003	Run 5	0.46 - 0.57 kft	272	500'
125003	125205	Profile 2	0.57 - 2.0 kft	276	500' - 2000'
125205	125308	Run 6	2.0 kft	274	2000'
125308	125517	Profile 2	2.0 - 4.0 kft	279	
125518	125623	Run 7	4.0 kft	279	
125623	125844	Profile 2	4.0 - 6.0 kft	270	
125855	125945	Run 8	6.0 kft	262	
130306	150451	Run 9	1.0 - 0.93 kft	243	1000'
144336		Videos	0.92 kft	242	Change tapes
150653	150707	Profile 3	-.04 - 0.00 kft	221	50'- 100'
150732	150808	Run 10	-.01 - 0.00 kft	222	100'
150808	150847	Profile 3	0.00 - 0.36 kft	223	100' - 500'
150847	150958	Run 11	0.36 - 0.57 kft	224	500'
150958	151127	Profile 3	0.57 - 1.9 kft	228	500'- 2000'
151127	151229	Run 12	1.9 kft	224	2000'
151229	151418	Profile 3	2.1 - 3.4 kft	222	3500'
151418	151706	Run 13	3.4 kft	224	3500'
152006	152422	Run 14	1.9 kft	246	2000'
152442	152846	Profile 4	1.9 - 6.0 kft	244	
152847	153424	Run 15	6.0 kft	276	
153812	160009	Run 16	1.9 kft	314	2000'
160134		ASPs	3.8 kft	029	Close
160856		Land	0.10 kft	021	At Cardiff
161354		Refuel posn	0.11 kft	119	51'23.98N, 3'20.56W
161631		INU	0.11 kft	309	Set to Align
165432		INU	0.10 kft	119	set to Navigate
170553		T/O	0.76 kft	122	From Cardiff
170702	171058	Profile 5	1.2 - 6.0 kft	120	
171058	171159	Run 17	6.0 kft	006	
171222	171401	Profile 5	6.0 - 8.0 kft	049	
171647	172439	Run 18	8.0 kft	042	
172816		ASPs	5.0 kft	082	Close
173900		Land	0.23 kft	356	At Cranfield
174237		Stop posn	0.22 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B092 Track 09-MAY-05

Generic Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B092

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date 09-May-2005

Outline schedule:

08:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
10:00 – Briefing
11:30 – Clear aircraft and security check
12:00 – Take off Cranfield
17:00 – Land Cranfield
17:30 – Debrief
19:00 – Power down

Location: Clockwise circumnavigation of England (East and South coasts)

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols through a round-Britain flight and to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the airmass in NNW wind direction.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be based on a circumnavigation of England 1000 ft, hugging the coastline along a pre-defined flight path. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) once or twice upwind and two to three times downwind of the source region. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO). These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region.

Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags. The Mission Scientist will generally broadcast on the Intercom channel, but switch to the 'Mission' channel when the flight deck is set to 'private'.

Sortie Detail

- a) Take off and climb to FL100 for transit to upwind leg of the operating area.
- b) T+10 start of background filter pack run 1; NO_x calibration (if available).
- c) T+60 end of filter pack run No 1; downwards profile from 6000 ft to 50 ft towards the coast East of Berwick upon Tweed, towards waypoint 56N2E, at 1000 ft min⁻¹; return to 1000 ft after profile.
- d) T+70 turn at waypoint 56N2E, back towards coast; upwind profile (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each), return to 1000 ft. at 2000 ft min⁻¹ (approx. 15.5 min profile duration)
- e) T+85 start of filter set No 2 along coast heading South; continue with 30-minute filter pack runs
- f) T+180 profile S of East Anglia (as d)
- g) T+230 profile at Channel Coast
- h) T+270 on reaching point 46, profile up (as d) for transit to Cranfield at FL100; NO_x calibration.

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Foster
2. Pilot 2 - Al Roberts
3. CCM – Gaynor Ottaway
4. CCM Training – Jim Crawford
5. Mission Scientist – Eiko Nemitz
6. Mission Scientist Training 1 – Ute Skiba
7. Mission Scientist Training 2 – Jonathan Smith
8. Flight Manager – Maureen Smith
9. Core Chemistry – Ruth Purvis
10. AMS – James Allan
11. Bag sampling 1 – Alan McDonald
12. Bag sampling 2 – Ivan Simmons
13. Filter sampling – Paul James
14. PTRMS – Anne Hulse
15. WAS – Maria Nielsdottir
16. NOxy – David Steward

Flight path:

Way Points

Cranfield			
77	55	40N	1 45W
??	56	00N	2 00E
77	55	40N	1 45W
79	55	00N	1 10W
80	54	05N	0 05E
83	53	30N	1 40E
40	52	41N	1 47E
41	51	53N	1 47E
42	51	05N	1 30E
43	50	40N	0 30E
44	50	40N	1 00W
45	50	01N	2 00W
46	50	01N	3 25W
48	50	50N	4 40W
49	51	22N	5 00W
Cranfield			

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when 1000ft is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value.

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated approximately every 60 minutes at 1000 ft. NO_x and SO₂ will be operated on a 0-50 ppb range.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximize sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN, PCASP, CCN are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal. Short warm-up time, due to earlier T/O.

TDL-AS: Operated during flight for CO₂ & CH₄.

NO_x: Operation as usual. Calibration during transits.

The flight started with a transit to the N. Sea area east of Berwick-upon-Tweed at FL100, just above the cloud tops. During take-off cloud base was found at 4500 ft, while the top of the boundary layer was at about 1 km. During transit the first filter pack run was taken, together with NO_x calibration and CO calibration. On reaching the coast a downward profile was flown (10,000 to 50 ft), where cloud base of the lowest cloud layer was observed at 1900 ft. From the coast a clean air run was flown east (filter pack run 2). At this point it became obvious that there was a mismatch between the flight plan and the actual fuel consumption, and the clean air run was cut short to preserve fuel so the SW corner of the UK (outflow) could be sampled fully. However, during the day the mismatch increased and the flight had to be cut short, a refueling stop at Cardiff became necessary (see below).

On westwards return of the clean air run, a stepped profile was performed from 50 to 6000 ft. The boundary layer height at this point was about 2800 ft. Following the original flight plan, flying commenced southward along the east coast at a flight level of 1000 ft. Here elevated CN concentrations were observed, while gas and aerosol mass concentrations were low. First indication of the outflow from the country was observed South of East Anglia, indicating that the westerly component to the mainly northerly flow was very weak. During the first (easterly) half of the westward leg along the Channel coast clear polluted air was observed with elevated concentrations of CO, NO_x, SO₂ and aerosol mass. However, a sea breeze developed on the westerly half, with southerly winds at low level. Following a profile and a 'toilet stop' at 6000 ft, the flight was commenced at an increased height of about 2400 ft, where the flow continued to be from NNW. In response to the fuel shortage, the original flight plan was aborted and the flight was re-routed to Cardiff for refueling. After take off from Cardiff time was tight to return to Cranfield within the opening hours of the airfield. No major measurements were made during transit to Cranfield. NO_x was post-calibrated, but at a reduced height of about 8000 ft, which was insufficient to clear all tops of the clouds determined by flight restrictions. Showers were encountered throughout the rather convective day.

Instruments problems: the CN counter associated with the AMS had initially been set to low flow mode and stopped seeing particles early in the flight. This was spotted and fixed. Later, the communication of the FAAM CN counter developed a fault, sending valid data to the logging system only every few seconds.

Clearly, only a part of the UK budget could be established during this semi-successful mission. Retrospectively, the flight may have been more successful with an earlier start in the day, as the sea breeze would have been less developed. Post-flight modeling will establish whether the full London plume was captured along the Channel coast.

Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.092**
FAAM © 2004

Date **9-05-05**

Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:00	start taxi		for	T/O	discrete with some ball at T/O
~ 11:06				T/O	
					cloud base at 4500 ft
					cloud top just below 10000ft
					Boundary layer height ~ 1000m
11:21:07	Run 1	1000			start start filter, NOxy cal, CO cal
11:59:34	Prof 1		just N of F7		10000 → 50
					cloud base @ 1900ft (lowest layer)
	short Run 2 @ 100m			aborted	
12:13	Run 2	start			1000 ft Run FILTER Run 2 CO cal.
12:17					discrete
12:41					U-turn start of start and of F7 Run 2 with Run 3 stepped profile
12:47					50/100/500/ ~ 2800 ft.
		3LN			
12:59					top of profile at 6000
13:11					start of filter pack run no 3 @ elevated CN
13:42					rig to the W
13:47					CN stopping, out
14:08					end of filter pack run
14:16					start of filter run 4
14:21					passing containers ship

com Flight Manager
Captain
Co

Flight No. Route Date Take Off GMTBag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-451	11:21:30	11:21:58			10,000 ft
-439	11:24:00	11:24:30			"
-464	11:27:00	11:27:30			"
-520	11:30:30	11:31:00			"
-492	11:33:00	11:33:30			"
-434	11:36:00	+30	53.6 N	0.7 W	"
-250	11:39:00	+30	53.8 N	0.8 W	"
-441	11:42:00	+30			"
-454	11:45:00	+30	54.2 N	0.8 W	"
-430	11:48:00	+30			
-498	11:51:00	11:51:30			
-245	11:54:00	+30			
-511	11:57:00	+30	54.9 N	1.1 W	
-402	12:00:00	+30			
555	12:03:00	+30			
455	12:06:00	12:06:25	55.4	1.4 W	
518	12:07:00	12:07:20			
415	12:08:00	12:08:30			1000 ft
005	12:09:00	+30			500 ft
558	12:09:46	12:10:16			50
456	12:11:30	12:12:00			Climbing to 1000
421	12:13:10	12:13:40	55.7 N	1.4 W	run at 1000
499	12:14:10	:40			
422	12:15:10	:40			
522	12:16:10	:40	55.8 N	1.2 W	
557	12:17:10	:40			
457	12:18:10	:40			
424	12:19:10	:40			
493	12:20:10	:40	56.0 N	0.9 W	
512	12:21:10	:41			
426	12:22:10	:40			
411	12:23:10	:40			Dropping to 800
513	12:24:10	:40	55.9 N	0.5 W	
425	12:25:10	:40			
435	12:26:12	:42			
241	12:27:10	:40	55.9 N	0.2 W	
406	12:28:10	:40			
436	12:29:10	:40			
444	12:30:10	:40			
403	12:31:10	:40	56.0 N	0.1 E	
427	12:32:10	:40			

Flight No. B092Route Date 9/5/05Take Off 11:00 AMBag Samplers: A. McDONALD I. SIMMONSSheet No. 2

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
413	12:33:10	:40			
433	12:34:10	:40			
412	12:35:10	:40			
240	12:36:10	:40	56°0N	0.7E	
410	12:37:10	:40			
500	12:38:10	:40			
553	12:39:10	:40			
309	12:40:10	:40	56°0N	1.1E	Humming at same altitude
367	12:41:10	:40			
414	12:42:10	:40			
260	12:43:10	:40			
551	12:44:10	:40	56°0N	0.8E	
560	12:46:49	:19			start at 70ft cloud & then climb
437	12:47:40	:10			100ft
416	12:48:30	:00			climbing to 500
429	12:49:20	:50			run at 500 (start)
445	12:50:10	:41			climbing
423	12:51:09	:35	56°0N	0.1E	climbing
432	12:52:10	:40			run at 2000
443	12:53:20	:50			climbing
428	12:54:10	:42			"
170	12:55:20	:50			run at 4000
453	12:56:30	57:02			climbing
438	12:57:30	:00			climbing
461	12:58:50	59:20			run at 6000
559	13:00:00	:30			falling
010	13:01:30	02:00			falling
145	13:03:10	:40	55.9N	1.0W	run at 1000
141	13:04:20	:49			
146	13:05:10	:50			
255040	13:06:30	:00			
142	13:07:30	:00			
143	13:08:30	:00	55.6N	1.3W	
530	13:09:30	:00			
163	13:10:30	:00			
166	13:11:30	:00			
164	13:12:30	:00			
168	13:13:33	:00	55.3N	1.2W	
149	13:14:30	:00			
147	13:15:30	:00			
165	13:16:30	:00			

Flight No. B0012Route Date 9/5/05Take Off 11:00 AMBag Samplers: A. McDONALD I. SIMMONSSheet No. 3

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
OLD 90	13:17:30	18:00			
191	13:18:30	19:00			
OLD 293	13:19:30	20:00	54.9N	1.1W	
9	13:20:30	:02			
198	13:21:30	:02			
OLD 262	13:22:30	:00			
200	13:23:30	:00			
196	13:24:30	:00	54.7N	0.8W	
OLD 293	13:25:30	:00			
195	13:26:35	:05			
OLD 154	13:27:30	:00			
192	13:28:30	:00	54.5N	0.5W	
199	13:29:30	:00			
OLD 4	13:30:30	:00			
OLD 1203	13:31:30	:00			
OLD 232	13:32:30	:00	54.3N	0.2W	
OLD 167	13:33:30	:00			
197	13:34:30	:00			
OLD 176	13:35:30	:00			
167	13:36:30	:00			
150	13:37:30	:00	54.0N	0.0E	
144	13:38:30	:00			
169	13:39:30	:00			
OLD 126/272	13:40:30	:00			
144	13:41:30	:00	53.9N	0.4E	
193	13:42:30	:00			
148	13:43:30	:00			
OLD 6	13:44:40	:10			
324	13:45:30	:00			
549	13:46:30	:00	53.7N	0.8E	
373	13:47:30	:00			
537	13:48:30	:00			
227	13:49:30	:00			
325	13:50:30	:00			
523	13:51:30	:00			
513	13:52:30	:00	53.5N	1.3E	
404	13:53:30	:00			
224	13:54:33	:03			
316	13:55:30	:06			
346	13:56:30	:00	53.3	1.5E	
489	13:57:30	:00			

Flight No. B092Route Date 9/15/05Take Off 11:00GMTBag Samplers: A. McDONALD I. SIMMONSSheet No. 4

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
531	13:58:30	1:00			
362	13:59:30	1:00			
374	14:00:40	1:00			
347	14:01:30	1:00			
272	14:01:30	1:00			
314	14:02:30	1:00			
470	14:03:35	1:05			
305	14:04:32	1:02			
547	14:05:30	1:03	52.7N	1.7E	
517	14:06:33	1:03			
524	14:07:30	1:00			
545	14:08:30	1:00			
239	14:09:30	1:00			
232	14:10:30	1:00			
214	14:11:30	1:00	52.4N	1.8E	
313	14:12:30	1:00			
316	14:13:30	1:00			
228	14:14:30	1:00			
449	14:15:30	1:00	52.1N	1.7E	
536	14:16:30	1:00			
534	14:17:30	1:00			
539	14:18:30	1:00			
229	14:19:30	1:00			
281	14:20:30	1:00			
375	14:21:30	1:00	51.9N	1.7E	
317	14:22:30	1:00			
343	14:23:35	1:05			
280	14:24:30	1:00			
401	14:25:30	1:00	51.5N	1.6E	
442	14:26:30	1:00			
259	14:27:30	1:00			
315	14:28:30	1:00			
302	14:29:30	1:00			
541	14:30:30	1:00	51.2N	1.5E	
535	14:31:30	1:00			
550	14:32:30	1:00			
221	14:33:30	1:00			
525	14:34:30	1:01			
319	14:35:30	1:00			
242	14:36:30	1:00			
293	14:37:30	1:00	50.9	1.1E	

Flight No. 16092Route Date 9/5/05Take Off 11:00 GMTBag Samplers: A. McDONALD I. SIMMONSSheet No. 5

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
290	14:38:30	:00			
282	14:39:30	:00			
203	14:40:30	:00			
516	14:41:30	:00	50.7N		
521	14:42:30	:00	50.7N	0.8E	
285	14:43:30	:00			
271	14:44:30	:00			
363	14:45:30	:00			
308	14:46:30	:00			
173	14:47:30	:00			
342	14:48:30	:00	50.6N	0.3E	
172	14:49:30	:00			
359	14:50:40	:10			
291	14:52:00	:30			
303	14:53:30	:00			
351	14:54:30	:00			
349	14:55:30	:00	50.6N	0.2W	
361	14:56:30	:00			
301	14:57:30	:00			
279	14:58:30	:00			
277	14:59:30	:00			
296	15:00:30	:00	50.6N	0.6W	
452	15:01:30	:00			
294	15:02:30	:00			
405	15:03:30	:00			
358	15:04:30	:00			end of run
355	15:06:51	:21			70ft fall then climb
374	15:07:30	:00			100 ft
366	15:08:15	:45			ascend
519	15:09:00	:30			500 feet
371	15:10:00	:30			climbing
273	15:11:30	:10			2000 feet
320	15:12:50	:20			climbing
341	15:14:30	:00			3500 feet circle at 3500
					circle at 3500 feet
295	15:20:10	:40			run at 2000 feet
304	15:21:00	:30			
469	15:22:00	:30			
307	15:23:01	:31			
171	15:24:00	:30			
257	15:25:00	:30			climb to 6000

Flight No. 15092Route Date 9/5/05Take Off 11:00 GMTBag Samplers: A. McDONALD I. SIMMONSSheet No. 6

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
274	15:29:40	1:10	50.0N	2.7W	at 6000 ft
298	15:36:20	1:50			descent to 2000 ft
346	15:38:00	1:30			2000 ft
283	15:39:00	1:30			
273	15:40:00	1:30	50.1N	3.6W	
345	15:41:00	1:30			crossing land
288	15:42:00	1:30			crossing land
365	15:43:00	1:30			
300	15:44:00	1:30			
258	15:45:02	1:32			
357	15:46:30	1:30			
299	15:47:00	1:30			
364	15:48:00	1:30			
287	15:49:00	1:30	50.6	3.6W	
251	15:50:00	1:30			
297	15:51:20	1:50			
286	15:52:00	1:30			
289	15:53:00	1:30			
292	15:54:00	1:30	50.8	3.4W	
356	15:55:00	1:30			
222	15:56:00	1:30			
360	15:57:00	1:30			
372	15:58:00	1:30	51.0N	3.1W	
276	15:59:00	1:30			
368	16:00:00	16:00	1:30		
284	17:10:00	1:30			
278	17:12:00	1:30			
344	17:13:00	1:30			climbing to 8000 ft
380	17:14:00	1:30			
174	17:15:00	1:30	51.6N	2.7W	
379	17:16:00	1:30			8000 ft
378	17:17:00	1:30			
376	17:18:00	1:30			
377	17:19:30	1:30	51.8N	2.4W	
350	17:21:00	1:30			
352	17:22:00	1:30			
354	17:24:30	1:30			started descending 9secs into sample

FLIGHT NUMBER	B092	DATE:	9/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP					

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	OK
All cylinders pressures are OK	OK
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	OK

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT			
POST FLIGHT			

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)		Pressure Cell (Torr)

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)							
NO (ppbV)							
NO ₂ (ppbV)							
NO _x (ppbV)							
SO ₂ (ppbV)							

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS
NO time for pre flight zeros as WAS and bag sampling needed refitting.

FLIGHT NUMBER	B092	DATE:	9/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP					

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL		Date and Flight Level		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	
		unknown							
Time	Flight Level	CO							
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
		83.39	88.03	7340.53		50.0	7.12		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)							
11:35:38	FL100	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
		33.83	0.65	0.75	1.075	0.066	0.358		
Time	Flight Level	CO							
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
		85.94	86.90	7468.19		49.62	7.14		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)							
12:15:58	1000ft	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
		34.02	0.4	0.4	1.112	0.067	0.473		
Time	Flight Level	CO							
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
		87.81	84.56	7465.66		48.54	7.13		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)							
13:12:42	1000ft	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
		34.02	0.6	0.4	1.108	0.067	0.471		
Time	Flight Level	CO							
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
		87.92	83.11	7307.42		48.46	7.14		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)							
14:08:20	1000ft	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
		33.98	0.6	0.4	1.110	0.067	0.472		
Time	Flight Level	CO							
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
		87.93	82.32	7239.24		48.49	7.15		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)							
15:41:15	2000ft	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
		34.38	0.6	0.4	1.114	0.068	0.462		

FLIGHT NUMBER	B092	DATE:	9/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP					

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample

FLIGHT NUMBER	B092	DATE:	9/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP					

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B092**

Date: 09/05/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	N	N
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	N
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	Y	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	N
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	N	
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	Racks:		
Nevzorov		Y	INC	Y	N
TWC		Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Only CNC
FWVS		N	CVI	Y	N
<u>Radiometers</u>					
Upper Clear	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
“ Red	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Nephelometer	Y	
“ JO1D	N		Filters	Y	Y
Lower Clear	Y	Y	AMS	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y			
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N				
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			<u>Others:</u>		
TAFTS	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
MARSS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
DEIMOS	N		VACC	Y	N
ARIES	N		PEROXIDE	Y	N
SWS	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			ADA	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ECGC	N		NOxy	Y	Y
NOX	Y	Y	PTRMS		Y
CO	Y	Y	Bag Sampling		Y
ORAC	Y	N			
PAN	Y	N			
PERCA	Y	N			
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B092

Date: 09/05/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off (mysteriously fixed self in flight...!).
2. Core Console fore laptop mains adapter lead missing from top drawer.
3. AMS – CPC stopped recording data in flight (~1230). Reset then okay.
4. PCASP – u/s
5. Core CNC – okay for 2.5hours then counts spiking to zero on HORACE. Raw data shows normal counts only apparent for about 6 to 8 seconds then jumps to 65535 for 8 to 12 seconds and continually cycling in that manner. Tried resetting instrument then restarting H_CNC to no avail.
6. FFC – window froze over en-route back from Cardiff (1715Z onwards).

Aircraft

1. Figures show us running below min fuel for Cranfield after 2 hours in flight (compared to flight plan data). The fuel-burn rate is ~1850kgs/hr. Had to cut corners and refuel at Cardiff to ensure sufficient holding fuel for Cranfield.
2. Intercom – CCM safety brief very quiet after landing. CCM2 brief very “muffled”.

Satcom-H calls made by FM: 2